

INTERACTIVE TEACHING METHODS IN CONTEMPORARY HIGHER EDUCATION

Raxmonova Matluba Janzakovna

Senior teacher of the department "Foreign Languages"
at the Tashkent Chemical-Technology Institute, Uzbekistan

e-mail: m.raxmonova2012@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8404870>

Abstract: In this article, modern teaching methods in higher education are analyzed, in which the improvement of lesson efficiency with the help of non-traditional methods is considered. Interactive methods are analyzed and seen with the help of examples.

Key words: higher education, interactive methods, interactive methods, lesson, education

In recent years, the education system of our country has been extensively implemented, with a substantive renewal of the higher education system at the heart of comprehensive reforms. Pedagogical activity in this educational system in an era of globalization of information has organized the educational process of the leading professors and teachers, covering important tasks such as modernization, application of innovative technologies to this process, and effective use of foreign experiences in this regard.

Today's pedagogue is responsible for the implementation of these tasks. Selection of innovative educational technologies related to educational content, design of training developments, and technological maps, defined in their ability to apply educational goals in practice, students' age, psychological, and based on their ergonomic features, it organizes education focused on the personality of the student is one of the urgent issues. As you know, in any study, the educational goal is of great importance in designing training.

Therefore, goal setting is the main factor in the technological design of pedagogical technology; the creation of educational processes and organizations begins with that. As you know, the goal is the expected result, considered as a product of an important direction in the form of a model of educational subjects, which is what they are expected to acquire at the end of the activity. The result, in turn, is that, firstly, the result obtained from the educational activity is the development of the learner, which is reflected in one or another of his activities.

And secondly, by demonstrating the effective progress of the educational process to the goal, which characterizes the level of achievement, the process of teaching and learning ends only when it fits the purpose. So, in setting educational goals, it is important that they fully correspond to the pre-planned results.

Innovative educational technology is education that includes some new or qualitative improvement of existing methods and tools in order to increase the effectiveness of the educational process and create conditions for educational activities that are most consistent with the current trends of socio-economic development. Methodology of organization of lim activity. Innovative activities in education include complex activities aimed at the emergence of innovations in the field of education. These innovations can be methods of organizing the educational process, resources used in the educational process, or scientific theories and concepts. Innovations develop through the use of research activities aimed at obtaining new

scientific knowledge, some kinds of discoveries, and inventions. In addition, the emergence of innovations can be the result of design work, in which instrumental and technological knowledge is developed that reflects the possibilities of practical actions based on existing scientific theories and concepts. Innovative projects are created, which later lead to the emergence of new technologies.

Innovative technologies in education make it possible to organize education and direct it in the right direction. Stereotypes that exist in the public mind affect the usual way of life, lead to painful events, and prevent the renewal of all types of education. The reason why people do not want to accept the innovations in modern education is because they are limited by their vital needs for comfort, security, and self-affirmation. Once the update process has started, it can only be stopped using special techniques¹

Therefore, innovative educational technologies in higher education mean methods based on the use of modern scientific achievements and information technologies in education. They are creativity and independence aimed at increasing the quality of personnel training by developing students. They provide interactive learning, increasing students' interest in the studied subject, bringing learning closer to everyday life practice (developing effective communication skills, adapting to rapidly changing living conditions, increasing resistance to psychological stress, teaching conflict resolution skills, etc.), and teaching methods of acquiring new sociological knowledge. This group includes:

- Student-centered educational technologies;
- Technology of group project work;
- Technology of command-module works;
- Information Technology;
- Health-saving technologies and more.

Interactive methods mean methods that activate learners and encourage them to think independently, with the learner at the center of the educational process. When these methods are used, the teacher invites the learner to actively participate. The learner is involved throughout the process. The benefits of a learner-centered approach include:

- study-learning with higher educational efficiency;
- high motivation of the learner;
- consideration of previously acquired knowledge;
- aligning the educational process with the goals and needs of the learner;
- support of the learner's initiative and responsibility;
- learning by doing;
- creation of conditions for two-way feedback.

Thus, the use of interactive methods in the process of teaching subjects has its own characteristics. Careful study and practical application of each interactive method used in educational practice expands the thinking of students and has a positive effect on finding the right solution to the problem. It increases the creativity and activity of students. When various theoretical and practical problems are analyzed through interactive methods, the expansion and deepening of students' knowledge, skills, and abilities are achieved.

Currently, the most popular interactive educational methods are:

¹ Xasanova M. Using innovative methods in higher education. Oriental renaissance: Scientific Journal, Volume 2, 2022

Interactive methods: "Case-study" (or "Educational cases"), "Blister survey", "Modeling", "Creative work", "Problematic education", etc²

Interactive educational strategies. The strategy for managing group work is based on the idea that, in a sense, interactive educational strategies and interactive educational techniques are distinct from one another; it is compared to strategic planning. In fact, these strategies are more related to interactive educational methods, and there are no other differences between them.

Interactive graphic organizers: "Fish skeleton", "BBB", "Conceptual table", "Venn diagram", "T-table", "Insert", "Cluster", "Why?", "How?" and b. The separation of interactive graphic organizers is based on the fact that the main ideas are expressed in written form in various graphic forms. In fact, working with these graphic organizers is more related to interactive educational methods, and there are no other differences between them.

Interactive educational methods are often used simultaneously with various forms of training technologies. By employing these techniques, training participants become more active and the educational process becomes more efficient.

One of the most serious didactic problems is the question of what depends on the choice of educational methods. In the didactic literature, it is noted that the correct selection of educational methods and the effectiveness of their application are related to various factors as follows: firstly, it depends on the didactic goals and tasks of training sessions; secondly, it depends on the nature of the material to be described; thirdly, it depends on the level of knowledge and development of learners; fourthly, it depends on the methods of the fundamentals of science studied in the educational process in a certain (current) period; fifthly, it depends on the conditions of the higher educational institution or department; sixth, related to the material and technical support of the educational process; seventhly, it depends on the teacher's pedagogical skills, his preparation and the level of organization of the educational process, as well as the teacher's knowledge of modern methods.

In conclusion, the process of professional education in higher education institutions is carried out within the framework of a multifaceted integrated system organized in accordance with modern forms and methods of education. In this case, each form fulfills the tasks set for itself, but the set of forms and methods forms a single didactic complex. The implementation of this didactic complex is determined by the psychological and pedagogical laws of the educational process.

² <http://shuhratbek.uz/interfaol-ta'lim-metodlari/>

References:

- 1.Xasanova M. Using innovative methods in higher education. *Oriental renaissance: Scientific Journal*, Volume 2, 2022
- 2.Karimova, G. M. (2021). Some comments on complete grammar. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(11), 200-203.
- 3.Mamatkadirovna, K. G., & Bahodirovna, N. S. The Principles of Determining the Mechanisms of Intertextuality of a Literary Text. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 4(1), 194-196.
- 4.Karimova Gulshod Mamatkadyrovna. (2022). The Role of Cholpon in Raising Uzbek Spirituality. *Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 15, 18-21.
- 5.Mamatkadirovna, K. G. (2022). Innovative Educational Technologies in the Educational Process. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 15, 108-110.
- 6.Mamatkadirovna, K. G. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF LISTENING AND UNDERSTANDING COMPETENCE IN TEACHING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE. *American Journal of Pedagogical and Educational Research*, 10, 150-153.
- 7.Karimova Gulshod Mamatkadirovna, & Tohirova D. J. (2023). METHOD OF TEACHING ANTONYMS IN MILITARY SYSTEM. *Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development*, 17, 110-112. Retrieved from <https://sjird.journalspark.org/index.php/sjird/article/view/759>
- 8.Karimova Gulshod Mamatkadirovna, & Sirayeva S. A. (2023). THE STRUCTION OF SYNONYMS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES. *Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development*, 17, 106-109. Retrieved from <https://sjird.journalspark.org/index.php/sjird/article/view/758>
- 9.Karimova, G. (2020). Some considerations about the process of lexicalization of grammatical units. *Результаты научных исследований в условиях пандемии (COVID-19)*, 1(04), 112-114.
- 10.Mamatkadirovna, K. G. (2023). THE BIBLE'S VIEWPOINT. *British Journal of Global Ecology and Sustainable Development*, 14, 65-67.

